

Using fixed filtering parameters in continuous wavelet transform for component separation of stimulus frequency otoacoustic emissions (SFOAE)

Uzma S. Akhtar^{1,a)}, Sumit Dhar², Renata Sisto³, Arturo Moleti^{4,b)}

¹Rush University Medical Center, Department of Communication Disorders & Sciences, Chicago, Illinois, USA

²Northwestern University, Roxelyn & Richard Pepper Department of Communication Sciences & Disorders, Evanston, Illinois, USA

³University of Rome Tor Vergata, Department of Physics, Rome, ITALY

⁴INAIL Research, Department of Occupational and Environmental Medicine, Epidemiology and Hygiene, Monte Porzio Catone (RM), ITALY

^{a)} Corresponding author: Uzma_Akhtar@rush.edu

^{b)} Moleti@roma2.infn.it

Abstract. Stimulus frequency otoacoustic emissions (SFOAE) in the ear canal are a mixture of multiple components with short- and long-latencies. These components can be isolated using continuous wavelet transform (CWT) filtering. However, the effects of varying filtering parameters on component separation have not been fully characterized. Swept-tone SFOAE up to 20 kHz were collected for two stimulus levels (30 and 36 dB FPL) in 64 human ears. SFOAE were filtered using both fixed filtering parameters and individually varied parameters. The effects of stimulus levels and age were also examined.

INTRODUCTION

Stimulus frequency otoacoustic emissions (SFOAE) primarily arise from the cochlear activity within the characteristic frequency region of the stimulating tone (Shera & Guinan, 1999), with potential contributions from basal sources (Charaziak & Siegel, 2015) as well as those resulting from multiple intracochlear reflections (MIR) (Dhar et al, 2002). While these additional contributions are less likely to dominate the total ear canal SFOAE, parsing the relative strength of individual components is important for: a) understanding the generation sources and mechanisms of SFOAE, b) relating them to other psychoacoustic or neural measures of auditory function, and c) characterizing the effects of various insults (e.g. aging, pharmacotoxicity, noise toxicity) on SFOAE.

The known relationship between frequency and delays measured in basilar membrane velocity or displacement (and presumably OAE delays) can be exploited to isolate contributions from different sources/mechanisms using time-frequency analysis techniques such as the continuous wavelet transform (CWT) (Moleti et al, 2012; Shera & Bergevin, 2012; Biswal & Mishra, 2018). Individual SFOAE components have previously been separated using multiple frequency-delay curves that use fixed time windows or windows that are adapted to maximize the magnitude of the OAE signal (Dhar et al, 2011; Moleti et al, 2012; Shera & Bergevin, 2012; Sisto et al, 2013).

A first broad separation may be performed by isolating the first-reflection component from multiple-reflection components of multiple delay. This is important because multiple delay components and spontaneous otoacoustic emissions (SOAEs) may produce unreasonably large delays. Then, within the first-reflection region of the time-frequency plane, basal and peak components (short-latency and long-latency) may be identified and separately studied (Sisto et al, 2013). The observed weak level dependence of the OAE delay (Sisto and Moleti, 2007) is more likely due to the observation that short-latency basal components grow more rapidly with stimulus level than peak components of longer latency, rather than due to a variation of the delay of the individual components (Sisto et al., 2013).

In animal models, latency cut-offs for separating single- and multiple-reflection components can be informed by measured basilar membrane delays (Charaziak & Shera, 2021). In humans, lack of knowledge regarding living BM delays necessitates the use of OAE delays instead. Many studies have reported on the SFOAE delays as a function of frequency (Schairer et al, 2006; Shera et al, 2010; Dewey & Dhar, 2016) and across different age groups (Abdala, Ortmann & Shera, 2018). Hence, these delays have been used to empirically optimize CWT filtering parameters (Moleti et al, 2012; Sisto et al, 2013). However, less is known about CWT filtering parameter optimization for different stimulus levels and different age groups.

The peculiar nature of the nonlinear cochlear response, which is significantly different from that of a classical resonant system, suggests that cochlear tuning, as inferred from OAE delay, is amply decoupled from cochlear gain. Indeed, a rather weak dependence of stimulus level on OAE delay (and of the corresponding tuning estimates) is experimentally observed, whereas gain is strongly dependent on level. Previously, Sisto et al (2013) showed that at a given stimulus level, the total energy of the late latency component of the SFOAE remains unchanged with different values of the CWT filtering parameters varied within a reasonably wide range. This suggests that fixed values of the CWT filtering parameters may be sufficient across ears. In this study, we compared SFOAE single-reflection components filtered using fixed and individually varied parameters to test the hypothesis that optimal CWT filtering parameters are not influenced by age. We also examined to what extent stimulus levels and age interact with the choice of filtering parameters for the estimation of single-reflection component.

METHODS

Participants: 64 normal-hearing adult humans, aged 18-45 years, participated in this study. All participants had normal otoscopic exam, middle ear function, and pure tone thresholds better than or equal to 20 dB HL from 0.25-8 kHz in the test ear. All participants provided informed consent and were compensated for their participation in the study. Procedures were approved by the Institutional Review Board at Northwestern University.

Equipment and Calibration: Experiments were controlled via custom written software in MATLAB (2015B) on an Apple Macintosh computer (Mac OS 10.12). Signals were presented through speakers housed in the Etymotic Research ER10X probe coupled to the ear with a silicone ear tip. Stimuli and recordings were routed through an RME Fireface 400 audio interface device at a sampling rate of 96 kHz and 24-bit resolution. Stimuli were calibrated in forward-pressure level after obtaining Thévenin-equivalent source and load characteristics in the ER10X calibration cavity for known cavity lengths and solving for load characteristics *in-situ*.

Measurement and Signal Processing: Swept frequency SFOAEs were recorded using the suppressor method for 33 sets of probe frequencies ($f_p = 0.375$ to 20 kHz) and two stimulus levels ($L_p = 30$ & 36 dB FPL). The frequencies were swept up logarithmically at the rate of 1 second/octave. Each sweep was approximately 0.25 seconds in duration. The suppressor f_{sup} was 47 Hz lower in frequency than f_p and fixed at 70 dB FPL across all f_p . Probe and suppressor were interleaved across four blocks of probe alone and probe+suppressor conditions where the suppressor phase was inverted in alternating presentations. Recordings ($n = 16$) were processed offline for filtering, cleaning, and time-domain averaging before they were sent through a least-squares fitting-based frequency domain analysis. SFOAE and noise estimates were corrected for individual ear canal acoustics and expressed in emission pressure level (dB EPL).

Time-Frequency Analysis: SFOAE spectra were processed using continuous wavelet transform (CWT) according to Moleti et al (2012). First, we created multiple frequency-delay functions, whose mathematical relationship can be described as $\tau = c_i a f^{-b}$, where $a = 13$, $b = 0.8$ and c is a constant for the i^{th} frequency-delay curve. In this approach, the values of the CWT filtering parameters a and b were fixed across all participants. Spectra were then filtered using the above described frequency-delay functions as the cut-off lines for first-reflection (including short-latency (SL) and long-latency (LL) components), and multiple-latency (ML) components. In the second approach, we obtained CWT filtering parameters a and b individually by fitting a power-law function (using MATLAB function *polyfit*) to the unfiltered SFOAE phase-gradient delay (UPG) from each ear, prior to any pre-filtering. The coefficients of the power-law fit were defined as a and b . These individualized coefficients were then used in creating multiple frequency-delay functions as described above to filter the SFOAE components. In the final approach, we obtained filtering parameters

a and b by fitting a power-law function to the average latency of the first reflection component using a wide pre-filtering band (PFB) with cut-off lines at $\tau = 6.5 * f^{-0.8}$ and $\tau = 19.5 * f^{-0.8}$.

Statistical Analysis: The total power within each filtered spectrum was compared across the three parameter estimation methods and probe levels. Values of power and parameter estimates that were outside of the 1.5*interquartile range from the median were considered outliers. Mixed-effects modeling was used to evaluate the effects of age, method and stimulus levels on the individualized filtering parameters a and b . Statistical significance was determined at alpha level set to 0.05.

RESULTS

Here we examined the effects of fixing or varying CWT filtering parameters on the total SFOAE power in 64 normal-hearing adult humans. We hypothesized that CWT filtering parameters are not significantly influenced by age, based on previously studied invariance of the SFOAE delays at low stimulus levels (Abdala, Ortmann & Shera, 2018). In order to test our hypothesis, we performed continuous wavelet transforms on all 64 ears at two stimulus levels of 30 and 36 dB FPL using both fixed and individually determined best-fit parameters. The individual best-fit parameters were obtained using both a gross measure, i.e. the unfiltered SFOAE phase-gradient delay (UPG), as well as a more refined measure, i.e. latency from a pre-filtered band (PFB) of the first-reflection component. We observed that varying filter parameters did not alter the width of the filtering bands significantly (Figure 1).

FIGURE 1. SFOAE and noise floor levels (left) and time-frequency contour plot (right) for one participant. Right: Red symbols indicate the SFOAE levels whereas black symbols indicate noise floor. Left: Cutoff lines computed using three different methods - fixed (pink), varied using average latency from a pre-filtered band (green) and varied using latency from the unfiltered phase gradient (blue) are shown for the same participant.

Figure 2 plots the best-fit coefficients a and b and their distributions as a function of age and stimulus level for fixed, pre-filtered and unfiltered parameter computing methods. Generally, we observed that the values of parameters a and b were similar for both stimulus levels and no obvious age-related trends were visible. A mixed effects analysis of variance (ANOVA) for coefficient a showed no effect of age ($F[1, 62] = 2.524, p = 0.117$), but there was a significant effect of method ($F[2, 310] = 4.210, p = 0.016$) and an age*method interaction ($F[2, 310] = 3.663, p = 0.027$). Similarly, the ANOVA for coefficient b showed no effect of age ($F[1, 62] = 3.470, p = 0.067$), but there was a significant effect of method ($F[2, 310] = 34.655, p < 0.001$) and an age*method interaction ($F[2, 310] = 4.656, p = 0.010$). The data shown in Figure 1 display large inter-subject variability, particularly when parameters are based on delay functions obtained using unfiltered phase-gradients (UPG).

The mean coefficient a and b for both stimulus levels and all three methods are summarized in Table 1. Compared to fixed $a = 13$ and $b = 0.8$, individual power-law fits to unfiltered phase-gradient (UPG) delays yielded values of both a and b that were higher and more variable. This is likely due to contamination from multiple delay components and/or SOAEs. Although using the UPG seems like an obvious choice for a first-pass estimation of latency cut-offs, this measure is likely not robust to measurement error, poor signal-to-noise ratio, and interference from multiple internal reflections (MIR).

On the other hand, a and b estimates obtained by fitting power-law to delays from a pre-filtered band (PFB) displayed normal and narrow distributions. The mean estimates from this method were lower than fixed values of a and b and similar to the best-fit values reported by Sisto et al (2013), although the current estimates were based on delay fits across a wider frequency range (0.375-20 kHz) compared to previous reports (0.5-5 kHz). The current report is also based on a larger sample size and thus could serve as normative data for future investigations.

Coefficients obtained using PFB did not differ by stimulus levels for either a ($F[1, 310] = 1.508, p = 0.220$) or b ($F[1, 310] = 0.111, p = 0.739$). This observation aligns with previous literature showing that OAE delays are largely invariant to stimulus levels and as such, optimization of CWT filtering parameters for different stimulus levels is unnecessary, at least for low stimulus levels. We explored this further by comparing the total power of the SFOAE spectra obtained for each stimulus level and method.

FIGURE 2. Individual best-fit estimates (circles) and corresponding box-and-whisker plots for coefficients a (top) and b (bottom) for both stimulus levels and both individually-varied methods of computing parameters. Color of the individual points represents the age of the participants in years with key in color bar. Outliers have been excluded for clarity.

TABLE 1. Means and standard deviations of coefficients by parameter estimation method and probe level for all 64 ears.

Method	Probe Level (dB FPL)	<i>A</i>	<i>B</i>
Fixed	30	13	0.8
	36	13	0.8
Varied _{Unfiltered}	30	14.65 ± 4.42	0.99 ± 0.13
	36	14.05 ± 3.99	0.99 ± 0.13
Varied _{Pre-Filtered}	30	10.56 ± 0.42	0.65 ± 0.03
	36	10.18 ± 0.49	0.63 ± 0.03

As seen in Figure 3, the total power integrated across the filtered first-reflection SFOAE spectra did not vary by method or stimulus level. Although the statistical analysis did not reveal an effect of age ($F[1, 62] = 0.521, p = 0.473$), method ($F[2, 310] = 1.488, p = 0.224$), or stimulus level ($F[1, 310] = 1.508, p = 0.220$), there was a slight trend for higher power with increasing stimulus level but only for the pre-filtered band (PFB) based method at 36 dB FPL. This suggests that while optimization may improve the response estimation slightly, it is not a significant improvement to using fixed parameters from established normative values. In the case of unfiltered phase-gradient delay (UPG) based method, the total power decreased slightly, compared to the fixed and PFB methods at 36 dB FPL. The underestimation of the total power of the first-reflection component using this method suggests that filtering parameters can have a significant effect on the estimates if prefiltering is not performed. Furthermore, optimizing filtering parameters using unfiltered phase gradients from less than ideal responses (poor SNR, multiple SOAEs, etc.) may in fact introduce more error in estimation of the individual components.

FIGURE 3. Total power (arbitrary linear units) of the filtered first-reflection SFOAE spectra using all three parameter computing methods and both stimulus levels. Panel headings indicate probe levels. Circles represent individual estimates for each corresponding box-and-whisker plot. Outliers have been excluded for clarity.

CONCLUSION

Using fixed filtering parameters provides a reliable estimation of the first-reflection component, at least up to 14 kHz. Above 14 kHz, there are ultra-fast components, either as a result of a scaling symmetry break, measurement artifact, and/or ear canal acoustics. Future studies could examine the nature of these ultra-fast latency components in combination with other measures such as wideband immittance/absorbance. Furthermore, the large inter-subject variability of parameters based on delays from the unfiltered SFOAE phase gradients highlights its susceptibility to various cochlear phenomena (SOAEs and MIR) and physiological conditions (i.e. hearing loss) that result in poor SNR. In summary, fixed filtering parameters are sufficient for estimating the first reflection component across low stimulus levels and in ears up to 45 years of age.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

Financial support for this work was provided by the NIH/NIDCD (F32-DC017352 [U.S.A.]) as well as the Graduate School and Knowles Hearing Center at Northwestern University and the College of Health Sciences at Rush University. We also thank the Mechanics of Hearing Workshop for providing travel support (U.S.A).

REFERENCES

1. Abdala, C., Ortmann, A. J. & Shera, C. A. Reflection-and Distortion-Source Otoacoustic Emissions: Evidence for Increased Irregularity in the Human Cochlea During Aging. *J Assoc Res Otolaryngol* 19, 493-510, (2018).
2. Biswal, M., & Mishra, S. K. (2018). Comparison of time-frequency methods for analyzing stimulus frequency otoacoustic emissions. *J Acoust Soc Am*, 143(2), 626-639.
3. Charaziak, K. K. & Siegel, J. H. Tuning of SFOAEs Evoked by Low-Frequency Tones Is Not Compatible with Localized Emission Generation. *J Assoc Res Otolaryngol* 16, 317-329, (2015).
4. Charaziak, K.K. and Shera, C.A., Reflection-source emissions evoked with clicks and frequency sweeps: Comparisons across levels. *J Assoc Res Otolaryngol*, 22, 641-658 (2021).
5. Dewey, J. B. & Dhar, S. Profiles of Stimulus-Frequency Otoacoustic Emissions from 0.5 to 20 kHz in Humans. *J Assoc Res Otolaryngol* 18, 89-110, (2017).
6. Dhar, S., Rogers, A. & Abdala, C. Breaking away: violation of distortion emission phase-frequency invariance at low frequencies. *J Acoust Soc Am* 129, 3115-3122, (2011).
7. Dhar, S., Talmadge, C. L., Long, G. R. & Tubis, A. Multiple internal reflections in the cochlea and their effect on DPOAE fine structure. *J Acoust Soc Am* 112, 2882-2897, (2002).
8. Moleti, A., Longo, F. & Sisto, R. Time-frequency domain filtering of evoked otoacoustic emissions. *J Acoust Soc Am* 132, 2455-2467, (2012).
9. Schairer, K. S., Ellison, J. C., Fitzpatrick, D. & Keefe, D. H. Use of stimulus-frequency otoacoustic emission latency and level to investigate cochlear mechanics in human ears. *J Acoust Soc Am* 120, 901-914, (2006).
10. Shera, C. A. & Bergevin, C. Obtaining reliable phase-gradient delays from otoacoustic emission data. *J Acoust Soc Am* 132, 927-943, (2012).
11. Shera, C. A. & Guinan, J. J., Jr. Evoked otoacoustic emissions arise by two fundamentally different mechanisms: a taxonomy for mammalian OAEs. *J Acoust Soc Am* 105, 782-798, (1999).
12. Shera, C. A., Guinan, J. J., Jr. & Oxenham, A. J. Otoacoustic estimation of cochlear tuning: validation in the chinchilla. *J Assoc Res Otolaryngol* 11, 343-365, (2010).
13. Sisto, R., and Arturo M. "Transient evoked otoacoustic emission latency and cochlear tuning at different stimulus levels." *J Acoust Soc Am* 122.4, 2183-2190 (2007).
14. Sisto, R., Sanjust, F. & Moleti, A. Input/output functions of different-latency components of transient-evoked and stimulus-frequency otoacoustic emissions. *J Acoust Soc Am* 133, 2240-2253, (2013).

COMMENTS AND DISCUSSION

Olha Fedoryk: Hi Usma S Akhtar and Team,

Thank you for this nice paper. The paper was easy to follow, the methods section was nicely structured and the results were discussed in a clear manner. A few suggestions/comments/questions on my end include expanding on why age had no effect and also discussing assumptions, limitations and further directions for this study.

Again thank you for this paper. I have attached the paper with my comments and questions.

Uzma S Akhtar: Dear Olha, thank you for your helpful comments and questions. Regarding the lack of age effect in our data, it is likely explained by the relatively young age of our participants (18-45 years) and only including those with normal-hearing through 8 kHz. This was part of the study design so as to avoid the confounds of hearing loss and declines in cochlear health from causes other than aging.

William Salloom: Hi Uzma and team, I attached my detailed review of the paper.

I have some comments and a question. It seems that both the fixed filtering parameters and the pre-filtered parameters for the continuous wavelet transform worked pretty well as latency predictors compared to the varied unfiltered parameters. The paper mentions that that some of this may be due to poor SNR, multiple internal reflections, and SOAEs. I am not sure how you would deal with the multiple reflections, but could you perhaps use a criteria on SNR and SOAEs in your dataset to determine how much of role they are in the variance and overestimation of latency in your dataset? In that case, if the SNR over the frequency range is poor or if there are enough large SOAEs to exclude those in your analysis to determine if the outcome is the same or not?

A second comment and question is that one of the factors in your analysis included subject age, but in fact, there were no effects of age on the type of analyses or probe level used. Was that expected necessarily? I think one of your references ([13]) had data showing that the phase slope in human which differed with age.

Uzma S Akhtar: Dear Will, thank you for your comments and questions. Regarding SNR, one of the advantages of using CWT is that improves signal to noise ratio, thus one can retain more data for computing phase gradient delays (see Shera & Bergevin, 2012). Similarly, effects of multiple-internal reflections/SOAEs can also be mitigated using techniques described by Shera & Bergen (2012) and Biswal & Mishra (2018), but we did not focus on this aspect for our comparisons. Finally, our sample was overall younger and had normal hearing through 8 kHz, which might explain why we do not observe any age-related effects on the phase slopes, similar to what was observed in the youngest two groups in Abdala, Ortmann & Shera (2018).